

GENERALIZATION OF CERTAIN MESTROVIC'S CONGRUENCE

M. Vasuki*, R. Sivaraman, Laid Elkhiri*** & J. López-Bonilla******

* Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Srinivasan College of Arts and Science (Affiliated to Bharathidasan University), Perambalur, Tamil Nadu, India

** Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, Dwaraka Doss Goverdhan Doss Vaishnav College, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

*** Department of Material Sciences, RECITS Laboratory, Tiaret University, Algeria

**** ESIME-Zacatenco, Instituto Politécnico Nacional, Edif. 4, 1er. Piso, Col. Lindavista CP 07738, CDMX, México

Cite This Article: M. Vasuki, R. Sivaraman, Laid Elkhiri & J. López-Bonilla, "Generalization of Certain Mestrovic's Congruence", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, International Peer Reviewed - Refereed Research Journal, Volume 9, Issue 1, January - June, Page Number 87-88, 2024.

Copy Right: © DV Publication, 2024 (All Rights Reserved). This is an Open Access Article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium provided the original work is properly cited.

Abstract:

Mestrovic [1] proved the following congruence:

$$\sum_{\text{odd } k=1}^{p-2} \frac{1}{k} \binom{p-1}{k} \equiv -q_p(2) \pmod{p^2}, \quad (1)$$

For any prime $p \geq 5$, where $q_p(2) := \frac{2^{p-1}-1}{p}$ is the Fermat quotient of p to base 2. In this brief Note, we use a result of Sun [2] to obtain an extension of (1) involving Bernoulli numbers [3].

Key Words: Bernoulli Numbers, Mestrovic's Congruence, Fermat Quotient, Congruence Modulo $p^2(p^3)$.

1. Introduction:

Glaisher [4] deduced the congruence:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{2^k}{k} \equiv -2 q_p(2) \pmod{p}, \quad (2)$$

For any prime $p \geq 5$, which it was extended by Sun [2]:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{p-1} \frac{2^k}{k} \equiv -2 q_p(2) - \frac{7}{12} p^2 B_{p-3} \pmod{p^3}, \quad p \geq 5, \quad (3)$$

where B_n are the Bernoulli numbers [3]:

$$B_0 = 1, \quad B_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, \quad B_2 = \frac{1}{6}, \quad B_3 = B_5 = B_7 = 0, \quad B_4 = B_8 = -\frac{1}{30}, \quad B_6 = \frac{1}{42}, \dots \quad (4)$$

In Sec. 2 we show the identity:

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{2^k}{k} = 2 \sum_{\text{odd } j=1}^n \frac{1}{j} \binom{n}{j}, \quad (5)$$

Then with (3) and (5) we shall obtain a generalization of (1). Here we consider the congruence relation modulo a prime power p^r extended to the ring of rational numbers [1].

2. An extension of Mestrovic's Congruence:

The expression (5) is valid, in fact:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{2^k}{k} &= \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \frac{2^j}{j+1} = \sum_{j=0}^{n-1} \int_0^1 (2x)^j dx = \int_0^1 \frac{(2x)^n - 1}{2x - 1} dx = \int_0^1 \frac{(2x - 1 + 1)^n - 1}{2x - 1} dx, \\ &= \int_0^1 \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} (2x - 1)^{j-1} dx = \sum_{j=1}^n \binom{n}{j} \frac{1 - (-1)^j}{2j} = \sum_{\text{odd } j=1}^n \frac{1}{j} \binom{n}{j}, \end{aligned}$$

thus (5) is immediate.

Now we employ (3) and (5) with $n = p - 1 \geq 4$ to obtain the following generalization of (1):

$$\sum_{\text{odd } k=1}^{p-2} \frac{1}{k} \binom{p-1}{k} \equiv -q_p(2) - \frac{7}{24} p^2 B_{p-3} \pmod{p^3}, \quad p \geq 5, \quad (6)$$

which represents our principal result.

References:

1. R. Mestrovic, Five curious congruence modulo p^2 , Math. Slovaca 65, No. 3 (2015) 451-462.
2. Z. H. Sun, Congruences involving Bernoulli and Euler numbers, J. of Number Theory 128, No. 2 (2008), 280-312.
3. J. Quaintance, H. W. Gould, Combinatorial identities for Stirling numbers, World Scientific, Singapore, (2016).
4. J. W. Glaisher, On the residues of the sums of products of the first $p-1$ numbers and their powers to modulus p^2 or p^3 , Q. J. Math. Oxford 31 (1900) 321-353.

5. R. Sivaraman, Bernoulli Polynomials and Riemann Zeta Function, Journal of Critical Reviews, Volume 7, Issue 17, (2020), pp. 1253 - 1260
6. R. Sivaraman, Properties of Bernoulli Polynomials, J. Math. Comput. Sci., 10 (2020), No. 5, pp. 2025-2032
7. R. Sivaraman, Bernoulli Polynomials and Ramanujan Summation, Proceedings of First International Conference on Mathematical Modeling and Computational Science, Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing, Vol. 1292, Springer Nature, 2021, pp. 475 - 484.